

WP8 - Technical progress & Planning Templates

Water-ForCE

Project Identification	
Project Full Title	Water Scenarios for Copernicus Exploitation
Project Acronym	Water-ForCE
Grant Agreement	101004186
Starting date	01.01.2021
Duration	36 months

Document Identification	
Deliverable number	D8.3
Deliverable Title	Templates
Type of Deliverable	Report
Dissemination Level	Public (PU)
Work Package	WP8
Leading Partner	3edata

History of Changes		
Date	Version	Comments
09.04.2021	V.0	First Draft for feedback from Coordinator

09.04.2021	V.1	Final Version made available to the Consortium
16.03.022	V.2	Reviewed version with KPIs table and Risk assessment added.

List of Acronyms

CSA	Coordination and Support Action
CT	Coordination Team
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PIP	Project Implementation Plan
WP	Work Package

Table of Contents

1.- Purpose of the Document.....	2
2.- Work Package Progress Report Template	3
3.- Task Planning Template.....	4
Annex 1.....	5
WP Progress Report Template	5
Annex 2.....	6
Task Planning Template	6

1.- Purpose of the Document

Following the description of the D8.3, this document includes the **”Templates for task planning and for WP Progress Reports”** of Water-ForCE CSA.

Included as part of the duties of the Coordination Team of Water-ForCE, and as it is reflected in the PIP (D8.4); internal technical reviews will be put in place twice a year (M4 and M9). These internal technical reviews are intended to help in the internal organization of every WP and also to allow the CT to detect any deviation from the expected quality or scheduled timing, thus helping to have any risk timely addressed and mitigated or solved.

All the templates are in a dedicated shared unit inside of the cloud system for digital documentation management put in place by the CT.

2.- Work Package Progress Report Template

This template (see Annex 1) provides the framework to describe all the needed information for the CT to monitor the implementation of the Action. Part of this information will have to be reflected in the Part B of the periodic technical report to the EC, thus also helping the beneficiaries to have it ready in advance. This information includes explanations of the work carried out by the beneficiaries during the reporting period in line with Annex I of the GA, the summary of deliverables and milestones, the deviations from the Work Plan, Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), Risk assessment or the description of the dissemination activities.

Other sections of the template respond to particular monitoring and organizational needs inside of the Action, as the evaluation of the task performance in terms of %. Similarly, being Water-ForCE a CSA and due to the internal structure of the project, the interaction between WPs is considered as a relevant process for the successful implementation of the action and it is included as a separate section in the template.

3.- Task Planning Template

This template (see Annex 2) provides the framework to subdivide the planned tasks inside subtasks following a timeline coherent with the rest of the tasks inside of the WP, and also with the due date of deliverables and milestones. This subdivision of tasks is intended to facilitate the monitoring progress of the tasks both to the CT and to the WP and task leaders, allowing them to set new internal milestones that help to keep track of the task performance.

This template has been made in a excel file in which every WP has its own spreadsheet, structured following the Gantt Chart included In the Annex I of the GA.

Annex 1

WP Progress Report Template

WPX Progress Report

Internal Review

M[X] dd/mm/YYYY

Water-ForCE

Project Identification	
Project Full Title	Water Scenarios for Copernicus Exploitation
Project Acronym	Water-ForCE
Grant Agreement	101004186
Starting date	01.01.2021
Duration	36 months

Table of Contents

1- Purpose of the document.....	2
2- WP Progress.....	2
3- Deliverables and Milestones.....	4
4- Deviations from the Work Plan.....	6
5- Dissemination Activities.....	7
6- Interaction with other WPs.....	7
7- Key Performance Indicators.....	8
8- Risk Assessment.....	11

1.- Purpose of the document

This document shall include brief information about the technical progress, results obtained (deliverables, milestones) and compliance with the Work Programme.

2.- WP Progress

Explanation of the work carried out until M[4]

Task and Objectives	Technical Progress
Task X.X Partners involved (during this reporting period)	Brief description % of the task accomplished
Task X.X Partners involved (during this reporting period)	Brief description % of the task accomplished
Task X.X Partners involved (during this reporting period)	Brief description % of the task accomplished

Task X.X	
Partners involved (during this reporting period)	Brief description % of the task accomplished
Task X.X	
Partners involved (during this reporting period)	Brief description % of the task accomplished
Task X.X	
Partners involved (during this reporting period)	Brief description % of the task accomplished

Table 1.- WP Progress description

3.- Deliverables and Milestones

Indicate If any deliverable was uploaded into the System:

Deliverable number	Description
Del X.X	Brief description Date of delivery:
Del X.X	Brief description Date of delivery:
Del X.X	Brief description Date of delivery:

Table 2.- Deliverables

Indicate If any milestone was met:

Milestone number	Description
M X.X	Brief description Date of delivery:
M X.X	Brief description Date of delivery:
M X.X	Brief description Date of delivery:

Table 3.- Milestones

4.- Deviations from the Work Plan

Deviation	Explanation
Task X.X Deliverable X.X Milestone X.X	Brief explanation of the causes of the deviation and mitigation measures taken. Do they affect other tasks?
Task X.X Deliverable X.X Milestone X.X	Brief explanation of the causes of the deviation and mitigation measures taken. Do they affect other tasks?
Task X.X Deliverable X.X Milestone X.X	Brief explanation of the causes of the deviation and mitigation measures taken. Do they affect other tasks?

Table 4.- Deviations from the Work Plan

5.- Dissemination Activities

Brief description of the dissemination activities carried out (presentations, conferences...)

6.- Interaction with other WPs

Briefly describe your interactions with other WPs and outcomes.

7.- Key Performance Indicators

Please fill the table with the values of the KPIs relevant to your WP.

Objective/Impact	KPI	Definition	Achieved reporting period	Overall target at the end of the project
Project Execution				
	Deliverables -KPI 1	N° of submitted deliverables		47
	Deliverables -KPI 2	Expected vs. actual delivery dates (difference in days: positive values reflect delay)		500
	Milestones	N° of Milestones achieved on time		18
	Consortium bodies meetings (GA – EB)	N° of meetings		15
Project Performance				
Engagement activities				
	Workshops	N° of workshops		8
	Webinars	N° of webinars		18
	Newsletters (external)	N° of Newsletters		5
	Links with other relevant projects/initiatives	N° of projects contacted		50

Increased coverage of EU Policies. Engagement of different stakeholders' typologies/Key users' identification

Total stakeholders engaged	N° of people registered through Hubspot	600
Sector activity: Science/ research	N° of people declaring activity	100
Sector activity: Water management	N° of people declaring activity	100
Sector activity: Environment management	N° of people declaring activity	100
Sector activity: Private/Industrial	N° of people declaring activity	100
Sector activity: Policy/regulator	N° of people declaring activity	100

Interest from stakeholders/key users

Project outcomes/documents	N° of downloads of project outcomes	500
Attendance to WP1 stakeholder workshop	N° of people attending workshop	150
Attendance to webinars	N° of people attending webinars	300

Experts input to the Roadmap. Interactions with Non-EO Communities.

Working Groups engagement	N° of experts	100
Non-EO Communities engagement	N° of Non-EO experts	50
Working Groups activity 1- meetings	N° of meetings of each WG	3
Working Groups activity 2- attendance	N° of experts attending the meetings	100
Attendance to the 2 major international workshops [MS12 & 13]	N° of attendees	200
Attendance to technical workshops (WP2-3-4-5)	N° of attendees	300

Geographical scope

Links with global initiatives	N° of links	5
Links with Africa	N° of links	5
Links with Asia	N° of links	5
Links with N America	N° of links	5
Links with S America	N° of links	5
Links with Australia/New Zealand	N° of links	5

Communication and Dissemination

Communications to conferences/workshops	N° of communications	20
Journal Papers	N° of papers	5
Special Sessions in Conferences	N° of Special Sessions. Delivered	6
Website visits	N° of unique website visitors	10000
Followers on Twitter	N° of followers	300
Twitter activity	N° of tweets	80
Followers on LinkedIn	N° of followers	200
LinkedIn activity	N° of posts	30
Followers on Vimeo	N° of followers	100
Activity on Vimeo	Videos produced	50

8.- Risk Assessment

Please fill the table with the information of the risks relevant to your WP. Add any new risk that you had detected and the mitigation measures taken.

Description of risk in GA	Proposed risk-mitigation measures in the GA	Influenced	Measures taken
Delays in WP activities.	Safe time frames have been established to absorb incidents in this WP		
Failure in the engagement of European Level decision makers (due to Agenda)	Organize WP6 meeting in Brussels		
Failure in the engagement of the technical part of Copernicus Services/Components	Organize an initial (WP1) meeting in Denmark, near EEA headquarters		
Failure in the engagement of the National Authorities	The partners who need it have a separate budget for the national stakeholders' engagement inside of WP1 (other direct costs). Support from these entities has been gathered in the proposal stage (Support Letters)		
A partner withdrawing from the consortium (Low due to earlier cooperation between the partners)	Process outlined in the Consortium Agreement. In most WPs there is enough expertise overlap to allow timely delivery of products		
Physical meetings cannot take place or need to be delayed because of the virus. People cannot travel between the countries.	Project has the possibility of delaying the meetings for some months. If the delays cannot take place, the leaders of WP and other members of the consortia have gained a lot of experience with videoconferences. Nowadays technology and experience will help us to have the meetings through video bridge.		

COVID 19 restrictions on travel and face-to-face meetings affecting the engagement of the key stakeholders and users through workshops and meetings.	Transform face-to-face meetings into virtual or hybrid formats.		
--	---	--	--

Description of identified new risk	Proposed risk-mitigation measures	Influenced	Measures taken
------------------------------------	-----------------------------------	------------	----------------

Risk - 1

Risk-2			
--------	--	--	--

Annex 2

Task Planning Template

WP/Task No	Subtask	WP/Task name	LEADER	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36
1		Policy, stakeholder and Service Analysis		M1.1																M1.2																			
1.1		Value chain and stakeholder identification												D1.1																									
	1.1.1	Subtask description																																					
	[...]																																						
1.2		Public domain and business sector identification												D1.2																									
	1.2.1	Subtask description																																					
	[...]																																						
1.3		Links between mission-service application																						D1.3															
	1.3.1	Subtask description																																					
	[...]																																						
1.4		End-user needs and requirements identification																						D1.4															
	1.4.1	Subtask description																																					
	[...]																																						
1.5		Innovation need and opportunities																						D1.5															
	1.5.1	Subtask description																																					
	[...]																																						
1.6		Contributions towards societal challenges, missions and SDGs																						D1.6															
	1.6.1	Subtask description																																					
	[...]																																						

WP/Task No	Subtask	WP/Task name	LEADER	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36																				
2		Water Quality Continuum																										M2.1													M2.2																		
2.1		Creating and Coordinating working group																										D2.1																															
	2.1.1	Subtask description																																																									
	[...]																																																										
2.2		Analysing current Copernicus WATER portfolio																													D2.2																												
	2.2.1	Subtask description																																																									
	[...]																																																										
2.3		Evaluating atmospheric correction methods																																														D2.3											
	2.3.1	Subtask description																																																									
	[...]																																																										
2.4		Developing higher level water quality related products																																																		D2.4							
	2.4.1	Subtask description																																																									
	[...]																																																										
2.5		Evaluating technical needs for future sensors																																												D2.5													
	2.5.1	Subtask description																																																									
	[...]																																																										

Water-ForCE is a CSA that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101004186.

WP/Task No	Subtask	WP/Task name	LEADER	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36
3		Water Quantity		M3.2																																			
3.1		Creating and Coordinating working group		D3.1																																			
	3.1.1	Subtask description																																					
	[...]																																						
3.2		Current and future Copernicus based services		D3.2																																			
	3.2.1	Subtask description																																					
	[...]																																						
3.3		Water management analysis		D3.3																																			
	3.3.1	Subtask description																																					
	[...]																																						
3.4		Using remote sensing in modeling		D3.4																																			
	3.4.1	Subtask description																																					
	[...]																																						
3.5		Future technical requirements		D3.5																																			
	3.5.1	Subtask description																																					
	[...]																																						

 Water-ForCE is a CSA that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101004186.

WP/Task No	Subtask	WP/Task name	LEADER	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36
4		Aligning <i>in situ</i> and satellite Earth observation activities		M4.1											M4.2																								
4.1		Creating and Coordinating working group		D4.1																																			
	4.1.1	Subtask description [...]																																					
4.2		Strengthening of in situ component for Copernicus calibration																									D4.2												
	4.2.1	Subtask description [...]																																					
4.3		Data integration within and between EO networks																									D4.3												
	4.3.1	Subtask description [...]																																					
4.4		Integration of innovative data sources																									D4.4												
	4.4.1	Subtask description [...]																																					
4.5		Innovative combinations of in situ sensors																									D4.5												
	4.5.1	Subtask description [...]																																					
4.6		Standardisation and open science																									D4.6												
	4.6.1	Subtask description [...]																																					

 Water-ForCE is a CSA that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101004185.

WP/Task No	Subtask	WP/Task name	LEADER	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36
5		Modelling and data assimilation		M5.1																												M5.2							
5.1		Creating and Coordinating working group		D5.1																																			
	5.1.1	Subtask description																																					
	[...]																																						
5.2		Value of satellite EO data to modelling																			D5.2																		
	5.2.1	Subtask description																																					
	[...]																																						
5.3		Exploring Artificial Intelligence																			D5.3																		
	5.3.1	Subtask description																																					
	[...]																																						
5.4		Future added value																			D5.4																		
	5.4.1	Subtask description																																					
	[...]																																						

Water-Force is a CSA that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101004186.

WP/Task No	Subtask	WP/Task name	LEADER	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36
7		Dissemination and Communication		M7.1																																			
7.1		Stakeholder engagement, dissemination and communication plan		D7.1																																			
	7.1.1	Subtask description																																					
	[...]																																						
7.2		Project webpage and outreach tools and materials		D7.2 D7.3																																			
	7.2.1	Subtask description																																					
	[...]																																						
7.3		Organisation of users and stakeholder workshops		D7.4																																			
	7.3.1	Subtask description																																					
	[...]																																						
7.4		Dissemination of project results and scientific communication		D7.5																																			
	7.4.1	Subtask description																																					
	[...]																																						

 Water-Force is a CSA that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101004186.

WP/Task No	Subtask	WP/Task name	LEADER	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	
c		Project Coordination and Management		M8.1	M8.2															M8.3	M8.4																			
8.1		Project coordination		D8.1																																				
	8.1.1	Subtask description																																						
	[...]																																							
8.2		Project management																																						
	8.2.1	Subtask description																																						
	[...]																																							
8.3		Project progress monitoring																																						
	8.3.1	Subtask description																																						
	[...]																																							
8.4		Documentation and data management																																						
	8.4.1	Subtask description																																						
	[...]																																							
8.5		Internal communication																																						
	8.5.1	Subtask description																																						
	[...]																																							
8.6		External communication																																						
	8.6.1	Subtask description																																						
	[...]																																							
8.7		Financial Management																																						
	8.7.1	Subtask description																																						
	[...]																																							
8.8		Communication with EC																																						
	8.8.1	Subtask description																																						
	[...]																																							

 Water-ForCE is a CSA that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101004196.

